

Galaxy populations across the proto-cluster to cluster transition

Star formation, quenching and structural evolution of galaxies in cluster progenitors at $z \gtrsim 1.5$

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Galaxy populations across the proto-cluster to cluster transition

Cluster progenitor environments at $z \sim 1.5-2.5$

1. clusters (and their progenitors) as likely most extreme environments in terms of environmental signatures \Rightarrow convenient laboratories to investigate “environmental processes” [e.g. talks by D. Baxter, A. Noble] affecting galaxy evolution in more general terms
2. easier to practically identify among other kinds of “environments”
3. probe cluster galaxy evolution back to main formation epoch
4. probe the transition between proto-cluster and cluster regime
5. high-redshift observations disentangle different aspects of galaxy evolution, where nature and relevance of environmental effects may change over time
6. constrain physical processes as a function of time and evolutionary phase of the structures

Cluster galaxy evolution as constrained by environmental signatures on galaxy populations

What “signatures”:

- ▶ **on broad star formation properties of the galaxy population**
 - quiescent fractions
 - sSFRs
- ▶ **on stellar population and gas properties**
 - stellar ages of quiescent galaxies
 - metallicity (stellar or (mostly) gas-phase)
 - cold gas fractions
- ▶ **on galaxy structure**
 - broad morphological properties
 - mass-size relation
 - gradients (color, sSFR, ...)
- ▶ **on nuclear activity**

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The fraction of star-forming and of late-type galaxies is lower than in the field and decreases towards the cluster center

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Star formation rate density is suppressed in cluster environments

Suppressed sSFR of star-forming cluster galaxies are consistent with slow quenching processes

But... at some point this picture has to change

Intermediate-redshift studies and early investigations at $z > 1$ found that a massive, red-sequence galaxy population was already in place in clusters up to $z \sim 1.3$, with estimated formation redshifts of their stellar populations $z_f \gg 2$, but...

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... NIR LF studies soon gave indication of deviations from passive evolution towards higher redshifts, suggesting an epoch of significant stellar mass growth in clusters at $z \gtrsim 1.4$

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... IR observations showed high levels of SF activity in distant clusters, possibly even rising towards higher density regions

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Star formation in high-z clusters — The “reversal of the SFR-density relation” ?

see many related talks
this week!

What do we ask - What do we see - What do we mean

“the density of star-forming galaxies rises sharply at smaller radii”

“major sites of star formation at this redshift”

14 ALMA detections in $r < 250$ kpc,
7x overdensity, $\text{SFR} \geq 1000 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$
(Ma+2015, Stach+2017)

Star formation in high-z clusters — The “reversal of the SFR-density relation” ?

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Tran+2015

projected SFR density (integrated)

projected SFR density per galaxy

but see next talk by B. Lemaux
for dense environments at $z > 2$

Star formation in high-z clusters — The “reversal of the SFR-density relation” ?

What do we ask - What do we see - What do we mean

Environmental dependence of the star-forming main sequence: sSFRs in (proto-)cluster environments are:

(slightly) suppressed?
(at lower masses and lower redshifts)

same as in the field?

possibly enhanced?
(in densest environments)

mass dependent ? also see talk by T. Kodama

see many related talks this week!

Cluster galaxies at $z \geq 1.5$ — clusters before quiescence ?

$z \sim 0.6$

van der Burg+2013, 2018

$z \sim 1$

$z \lesssim 1$

$z \geq 1.5$

Cluster galaxies at $z \gtrsim 1.5$ — clusters before quiescence ?

... correspondingly, a drop in environmental quenching efficiency beyond $z \gtrsim 1.5$

$$\text{environmental quenching efficiency} = \frac{f_{q,cluster} - f_{q,field}}{1 - f_{q,field}}$$

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What is the “field” and its use as a reference:

- in most studies, the reference field is a large(r) region of the Universe, which thus contains a broad range of environments
- however, “field” galaxies might not be representative of galaxies infalling into clusters (e.g. **Werner+2022**, **Ahad+2023**), which would impact the derived estimate of environmental quenching and of its properties
- the environmental quenching efficiency as measured against the “field” thus probes a combination of quenching processes related to the “cluster environment” in different ways

Werner+2022

Cluster galaxies at $z \gtrsim 1.5$ — clusters before quiescence ?

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But at the same time... the quiescent view

see many related talks this week!

But at the same time... the quiescent view

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But at the same time... the quiescent view

... and at least some examples of efficiently quenched populations even among proto-clusters up to $z \gtrsim 3$!

Ito+2023, $z \sim 2.8$

McConachie+2022, $z \sim 3.4$

see related talks
later / tomorrow

see many related talks
this week!

How significant is environmental quenching in high-redshift clusters ?
When and how are cluster galaxy populations transitioning to the quiescent regime ?
In which clusters? Where within clusters ? At what stellar mass?

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200 kpc

Strazzullo+2016/2018

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[galaxy sample selection / completeness, stellar mass limit (vs potentially mass-dependent environmental quenching), global vs local environment, consistent estimate / comparison of clustercentric distances, ...]

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— possibly with a dependence on cluster mass

[looser definition of “clusters” at this redshift, comparison of structures with very different halo masses, and often with poorly constrained cluster masses in the first place, and thus also cluster radii ...]

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 - possibly highlighted by some amount of cluster selection bias

[different cluster selection approaches may (to different extent) preferably identify clusters with different galaxy population properties ...
Particularly critical for biased tracers...]

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 - possibly with a dependence on cluster mass
 - possibly highlighted by some amount of cluster selection bias
- ◆ **on top of all this, the intrinsic complications / limitations coming from often poor statistics of both cluster and cluster galaxy samples affecting studies at this redshift**

Environmental dependence of structural properties

broad morphological properties correlate with quiescence at least up to $z \sim 2$

Bell+2012

Environmental dependence of structural properties

The morphology-density relation evolves...

Environmental dependence of structural properties

... but it is observed at least in some clusters even up to $z \sim 2$

Environmental dependence of structural properties

— still tightly related to star-formation suppression ?

Strazzullo+2023

Environmental dependence of structural properties

— still tightly related to star-formation suppression ?

see also talk by S. Mei later
note possible redshift rdependence?

morphology-density relation

largely connected to high quiescent fraction

Environmental dependence of galaxy sizes ?

The redshift evolution of the mass-size relation of (quiescent and star-forming) field galaxies

Environmental dependence of galaxy sizes ?

see yesterday's talk
by A. Afanasiev!

— quiescent and/or early-type galaxies

Environmental dependence of galaxy sizes ?

— quiescent and/or early-type galaxies

Potential dependence on:
 — properties of investigated structures?
 — galaxy sample selection?
 — measurement / analysis bias?
 — ... ?

Environmental dependence of (early-type) galaxy sizes ?

mass-size relation in $z \sim 1$ clusters **lower** than in the field because of lack of growth through minor mergers

mass-size relation in $z \geq 0.6$ clusters **higher** than in the field because of accelerated evolution at early times

Environmental dependence of galaxy sizes ?

— star-forming and/or disk galaxies

Perez-Martinez+2023

field, quiescent (vdW+14)
 field, star-forming (vdW+14)
 field, Q
 field, SF

all clusters
(scaled to $z=1.5$)

Strazzullo+2023

see talk by J. Perez-Martinez tomorrow!

Environmental dependence of galaxy sizes ?

— star-forming and/or disk galaxies

cluster vs. field difference in size ratio of H α and stellar continuum sizes

Perez-Martinez+2023

Matharu+2021

... and finally:

Since >10 years we can observe cluster galaxies at this critical cosmic time. Still, we suffer from the **lack of detailed information on statistical and representative samples of both clusters and cluster galaxies:**

[critical and immediately relevant to what discussed]

— reliable SFR tracers

— “wide-field” deep, high-resolution photometry probing the full cluster virial volume and beyond

— sufficiently large and unbiased cluster samples over a sufficiently large mass range (with reliable masses)

— sufficiently large and complete galaxy samples spanning a sufficiently large stellar mass range

— deep spectroscopic follow-ups reducing uncertainties on cluster membership and improving constraints on galaxy properties (in particular stellar ages)

[equally critical and tightly related to what discussed: gas mass measurements, AGN tracers, metallicity estimates, ICM characterization, ..., ..., ...]

Although comparison with simulations is not trivial, **a theoretical framework is needed to extend the reach of observations a bit closer to constraints on physical processes**, within a proper cosmological context and accounting for the complex environmental history of a galaxy throughout its life.